

**CUSTOMERS' SATISFACTION TOWARDS THE SERVICE QUALITY OF
DIGITAL BANKING SERVICES ----- A STUDY IN VISAKHAPATNAM
DISTRICT OF ANDHRA PRADESH**

*** Ch. Lakshmi Bharati**

Research Scholar
Department of Commerce and Bus. Admn.
Acharya Nagarjuna University ,Guntur

**** Prof. R.Sivarama Prasad**

Research Supervisor
Department of Commerce and Bus. Admn.
Acharya Nagarjuna University, Guntur

ABSTRACT

The rapid advancement of digital technology has transformed various aspects of our lives, including the way we conduct financial transactions. E-banking, also known as electronic banking, has emerged as a revolutionary mode of delivering financial services, allowing customers to perform banking activities electronically through digital platforms. The study examines the satisfaction levels of the respondents towards Digital banking services and it analyzes the association between the demographic profile of the respondents and their level of satisfaction towards Digital banking services. The present study adopts Qualitative and Descriptive Research design. Both primary and secondary data were analyzed for drawing the conclusive inferences from this study. The sampling area selected for the study is Visakhapatnam district of Andhra Pradesh. Six banking organizations comprising three public and three private banks were selected as the sampling units and Proportionate Random sampling technique was applied to draw the sample respondents from the identified sampling units and the total sample size stands at 150 sample respondents. Interview schedule method was applied for recording the responses from the sample respondents. The statistical tools like percentages and Chi-square test were applied for drawing the inferences from the study. The study finally concludes that there exists a significant association between the demographic factors of the respondents and their level of satisfaction towards Digital banking services.

Key Words: Demographic factors, Digital Banking services, Satisfaction Level

INTRODUCTION

Digital payments are more convenient than cash payments. You do not need to carry a lot of cash with you all the time. You can make digital payments in seconds. The change is not a concern with digital payments when you can pay the exact amount. Hence, we can say that a Digital payment is the future of fund transfer and money transactions. The payment system in any country needs to pass the litmus test of safety, security, soundness, efficiency, and accessibility. In order to address all these, payment systems have evolved from barter to currency, to digital systems. We are witnessing enormous change in the payment systems, disrupting the monopoly of physical/paper-based system by electronic ones.

The rapid advancement of digital technology has transformed various aspects of our lives, including the way we conduct financial transactions. E-banking, also known as electronic banking, has emerged as a revolutionary mode of delivering financial services, allowing customers to perform banking activities electronically through digital platforms. This paradigm shift has not only altered the landscape of the banking industry but has also significantly impacted consumer behavior toward financial services.

Additionally, the implementation of intrusion detection systems and various virus protection measures ensures that digital banking services remain safe and secure. Customers of banks or other financial institutions can perform a variety of financial transactions via the website of the financial institution by using online banking, also referred to as Digital banking, which is an electronic payment system. The online banking system will typically connect to or be part of the core banking system operated by a bank, and is in contrast to branch banking, which was the traditional way customers accessed banking services. These days, "virtual banks" (also known as "direct banks") only have an online presence, which allows them to charge less than conventional banks with physical locations. Customer relations in banks Service quality:

The bankers provide their customers with consistent service quality, ensuring no discrimination based on nationality, religion, financial background, social status, or gender. While differences may arise from the targeted marketing strategies,

organizational structures, and the range of products offered, particularly in how they approach high-risk clients these should not be viewed as indications of bias or categorization among customers. Handling the customer complaints: They look into the causes of customer complaints and implement necessary steps to prevent them from happening again.

Additionally, employees are informed about any errors in practices and receive guidance to correct these mistakes and ensure they do not occur in the future. Security: With the evolution of their services in response to technological advancements, banks are committed to implementing necessary technical and legal measures to ensure the security of all processes across various service media and channels, protecting customers from potential victimization. They will uphold the highest standards of security when it comes to safeguarding customers' assets, including deposits, share certificates, bonds, bills, and confidential information. Additionally, banks will ensure the integrity of their offerings, such as credit and interest facilities, without compromise.

A digital bank represents a virtual process that includes online banking and beyond. As an end-to-end platform, digital banking must encompass the front end that consumers see, the back end that bankers see through their servers and admin control panels and the middleware that connects these nodes. Ultimately, a digital bank should facilitate all functional levels of banking on all service delivery platforms. In other words, it should have all the same functions as a head office, branch office, online service, bank cards, ATM and point of sale machines. Digital banking is getting more and trendier among the consumers. Digital payments are growing in India as the consumers are relying upon the digital life style to make things convenient and faster and the consumers are embracing digital payment with open arms.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ansari, Seharish J. & Khan, Nisar A. (2017) have tried to analyze the progress and challenges of ebanking in India from 2011 to 2016, also throwing some light on the status of retail electronic payments in the post-demonetization period. Post

demonetisation i.e., from November 2016 to May 2017, RTGS (real time gross settlement), NEFT (national electronic fund transfer) and UPI (unified payments interface) increased at a CAGR of 4.72%, 1.95% and 60.50% respectively. Mobile banking declined continuously. Their study also mentions the challenge of increasing number of Digital users and the requirement of banks to be able to meet out the expectations of these tech savvy people.

Chauhan, V. & Chaudhary, V. (2015) focused on understanding the concept of Digital banking and its benefits from the perspective of consumers as well as banks and the current scenario of Digital banking. They concluded that most of the banks have implemented e-banking facilities that are beneficial both for the consumers and the banks but then there are issues of safety, security, and reliability which the banks must adhere to.

Manikyam, Ratna (2014) analyzed the impact of liberalization, privatization, and globalization on Indian banks and the resultant opportunities and challenges. The study revealed that the biggest challenges for banking challenge for the mass and companies and those Indian banks should come up with differentiated products to stand at par with foreign banks. Further, the study also emphasized building knowledge-driven organizations for surviving the competition from the banks globally.

Haq & Khan (2013) analyzed the challenges and opportunities in the Indian Banking sector. It observed that qualifications in terms of education and income of the respondents were playing the role in the acceptance of online banking. The study suggested that it is the need of time that financial literacy of the users should be increased through various programs which should be run by banks to increase the awareness of Digital banking.

Seranmadevi, R (2012). Various e-Banking can be attractive to potential customers in terms of improved accessibility, affordability, and ease of use. It also focuses on the functionality of electronic credit cards, frequency of usage, mode of repayment, value addition facilities offered along the credit cards for different client groups.

Dangwal, R.C. (2010). Technology is growing rapidly and undergoing many changes. It indicates the unification of communication technology, information systems, and innovative applications to product manufacturing, design, and control. With the advancement in technology, the world has become a global village and ushered in a revolution in the banking sector.

Servon, (2008). Digital banking is revolutionizing the financial industry and banking now is no longer limited to branches, depositing, or withdraw cash. With the increase in technology computer banking, direct deposits, stored value card is being used.

According to Saleh and Andrea (2002), electronic banking is procuring banking services via e- delivery channels. Though, different scholars defined the term electronic banking in a different ways all agreed up on that E-banking is getting/accessing bank services through ATM's, PC's, mobile devices etc. at anytime and anywhere which ensures throughout a day including weekends, even on holidays. There is no necessity for customers to travel to banks location for making transactions like deposits, withdrawal or for any applications.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

1. To study the demographic profile of the respondents in the study area
2. To examine the satisfaction levels of the respondents towards the service quality of digital banking services
3. To analyze the association between the demographic profile of the respondents and their level of satisfaction towards digital banking services.
4. To suggest certain measures for the effective implementation of the quality of digital banking services in order to promote the satisfaction levels of the customers in the study area.

NULL HYPOTHESES

Ho1 : There is no significant association between the age of the respondents and their satisfaction levels towards digital banking services

Ho2 : There is no significant association between the gender of the respondents and their satisfaction levels towards digital banking services

Ho3 : There is no significant association between the educational qualification of the respondents and their satisfaction levels towards digital banking services

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study adopts Qualitative and Descriptive Research design. Both primary and secondary data were analyzed for drawing the conclusive inferences from this study. The sampling area selected for the study is Visakhapatnam district of Andhra Pradesh. The sample respondents identified for the present study comprises bank customers selected from the sampling units which encompass three public sector and three private sector banking organizations. The public sector banks selected for the study comprise State Bank of India , Indian Overseas Bank, Central Bank of India and the private sector banks selected for the study comprise ICICI ,HDFC and Axis banks.

Proportionate Random sampling technique was applied to draw the sample respondents from the identified sampling units. 25 sample respondents from every identified banking organization were selected and hence the total sample size stands at 150 sample respondents drawn from the identified six banking organizations. Interview schedule method was applied for recording the responses from the sample respondents. The statistical tools like percentages and Chi-square test were applied for drawing the inferences from the study.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION**Table No.1****Age and Level of satisfaction towards Digital banking services**

Age (in years)	Level of Satisfaction			Total	Percentage
	Low	Medium	High		
Below 25	4	5	7	16	10.7
25-40	7	12	21	40	26.7
41-50	7	18	34	59	39.3
Above 50	6	10	19	35	23.3
Total	24	45	81	150	100

Source : Primary Data

The table no. 1 shows the age details of the respondents in the study units. It shows that 10.7 percent of the respondents are in the age category of below 25 years, 26.7 percent of the respondents are in the age category of 25-40 years, 39.3 percent of the respondents are in the age category of 41-50 years and 23.3 percent of the respondents are in the age category of above 50 years.

The result shows that majority of them are highly satisfied towards the quality of Digital banking services.

Table No.2**Gender and Level of satisfaction towards Digital banking services**

Gender	Level of Satisfaction			Total	Percentage
	Low	Medium	High		
Male	12	29	73	114	76.0
Female	8	11	17	36	24.0
Total	20	40	90	150	100

Source : Primary Data

The table no.2 shows the gender details of the respondents and their satisfaction levels towards Digital banking services. It shows that 76.0 percent of the respondents are males and 24.0 percent of the respondents are females by their gender. The result shows that majority of them are highly satisfied towards the quality of Digital banking services.

Table No.3
Education Qualification and Level of satisfaction towards
Digital banking services

Education Qualification	Level of Satisfaction			Total	Percentage
	Low	Medium	High		
Up to SSC	2	3	6	11	7.3
Intermediate	4	5	12	21	14.0
Graduation level	11	23	50	84	56.0
Others	7	11	16	34	22.7
Total	24	42	84	150	100

Source : Primary Data

The table no.3 shows the education level of the respondents and their satisfaction level towards Digital banking services. It shows that 7.3 percent of the respondents are having educational qualification up to SSC level, 14.0 percent of the respondents are having educational qualification upto intermediate level, 56.0 percent of the respondents are graduates and 22.7 percent of the respondents are having other educational qualifications. The result shows that majority of the respondents are graduates and they are highly satisfied towards the quality of Digital banking services .

Verification of Hypothesis – Ho1

Ho1 : There is no significant association between the age of the respondents and their satisfaction levels towards Digital banking services

Test applied : Chi-square test

Table No. 4**Association between the age of the respondents and their level of satisfaction**

Tests	Value	df	Sig.
Pearson Chi-square	12.734	6	0.032
Likelihood ratio	11.396	6	0.036
Linear – by – Linear association	1.168	1	0.002

Source : computed

Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The chi-square denotes that the chi-square value was found to be 12.734 and the likelihood ratio found to be 11.396 and the linear –by-linear association was found to be 1.168 and they are found to significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the proposed null hypothesis (Ho1) is rejected. Thus, it can be inferred from the study results that there is a significant association between the age of the respondents and their satisfaction levels towards Digital banking services

Verification of Hypothesis – Ho2

Ho2 : There is no significant association between the gender of the respondents and their satisfaction levels towards Digital banking services

Test applied : Chi-square test

Table No.5**Association between the gender of the respondents and their level of satisfaction**

Tests	Value	df	Sig.
Pearson Chi-square	25.392	2	0.000
Likelihood ratio	24.815	2	0.000
Linear – by – Linear association	1.218	1	0.002

Source : computed

Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The chi-square denotes that the chi-square value was found to be 25.392 and the likelihood ratio found to be 24.815 and the linear –by-linear association was found to be 1.218 and they are found to significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the proposed null hypothesis (Ho2) is rejected. Thus, it can be inferred from the study results that there is a significant association between the gender of the respondents and their satisfaction levels towards Digital banking services

Verification of Hypothesis – Ho3

Ho3 : There is no significant association between the educational qualification of the respondents and their satisfaction levels towards Digital banking services

Test applied : Chi-square test

Table No.6

Association between the educational qualification of the respondents and their level of satisfaction

Tests	Value	df	Sig.
Pearson Chi-square	32.694	6	0.000
Likelihood ratio	28.734	6	0.000
Linear – by – Linear association	1.036	1	0.004

Source : computed

Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The chi-square denotes that the chi-square value was found to be 32.694 and the likelihood ratio found to be 28.734 and the linear –by-linear association was found to be 1.036 and they are found to significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the proposed null hypothesis (Ho3) is rejected. Thus, it can be inferred from the study results that there is a significant association between the educational qualification of the respondents and their satisfaction levels towards Digital banking services

CONCLUSION

The present study examines the customers level of satisfaction towards the service quality of Digital banking services. The study examines the demographic profile of the respondents in the study area and it was found that majority of the respondents were found to be in the age group of 41-50 years, majority of them are found to be males and a major proportion of the respondents had their educational qualifications up to graduation level.

The study further reveals that with regard to the level of satisfaction among the customers, a major proportion of the respondents categorized by their age, gender and educational qualifications had opined that they are highly satisfied towards the service quality of Digital banking services.

The study further examines the association between the demographic factors of age, gender, educational qualifications and their level of satisfaction towards the service quality of Digital banking services and it was statistically found to be significant. Thus, the study finally concludes that there exists a significant association between the demographic factors of the respondents and their level of satisfaction towards Digital banking services.

SUGGESTIONS

- Assessing the problems in the implementation process of service quality attributes
- Formulating the strategy to overcome transactional and technical hurdles under the context of customers perspective.
- The banking organizations shall introduce more user friendly Digital banking applications for the customers.

REFERENCES

- Ansari, Seharish J & Khan, Nisar A (2017). E-Banking in India: Progress and Challenges. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies*, Volume 4, Issue 8, pp 334-340.
- Chauhan, V and Chaudhary, V (2015). Digital Banking in India: Challenges and Opportunities in Indian Context. *Journal of Management Sciences and Technology*, Vol.2(3), pp 29-40.
- Dangwal..R.C., K. S. (January 2010). *The upcoming Technology and the associated innovations*. sfo, ca: The ICFAI University Press.
- Haq, S., Khan, M. (2013). E-banking challenges and opportunities in the Indian banking sector. *Innovative Journal of Business and Management*, 2(4), 56-59.
- Saleh, M. N. (2002). Challenges of the 'E-Banking Revolution. In A quarterly magazine of International Monetary Fund (Vol. 39).
- Manikyam, K. Ratna (2014). Indian Banking Sector- Challenges and Opportunities. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, Volume 16, Issue 2. Ver.1, pp 52-61.
- Seranmadevi R MG., Saravanaraj (2012). An Empirical Study on Quality of Digital Banking Services in India. *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Sciences*, (52).
- Servon, L. a. (2008). Consumer financial literacy and the impact of online banking on the financial behavior of lower-income bank customers', *Journal of Consumer Affairs* (Vol. 42).